

CoARA Action Plan 2024-2028 University of Gdańsk, Poland

The University of Gdańsk is a modern university established in 1970, located by the Baltic Sea, with the motto: "In mari via tua". Autonomy, creativity and commitment to the development of the highest quality education and improvement of scientific research combined with respect for tradition and concern for integrating the scientific community in the business environment constitute the recognizable brand of the University of Gdańsk in Poland, Europe and around the world. The University of Gdańsk has the ambition to be a research university, actively participating in developing scientific culture at the national and international level, based on the management by values model, promoting interdisciplinary scientific communication, cooperation and creative involvement, and building an academic community. The University of Gdańsk is open to all those who with their knowledge, creative commitment and attitude, contribute to strengthening its rank and work for the prosperity of the academic community for the common good.

The vision of the University of Gdańsk included in the Development Strategy for 2019-2025

THE ROAD TO THE REFORM OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

The University of Gdańsk consistently undertakes strategic action related to improving the working conditions of the entire academic community, including ensuring the highest standards in the field of recruitment, assessment and promotion of employees in compliance with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers. Some of the tasks were already included in the *HR Excellence in Research* strategy in 2016, then updated and revised several times. A few key changes confirming the implementation of the HR strategy include the adoption of the Policy for the Development of Open Access to Scientific Publications (2017 and 2022 update); signing of the Declaration of Social Responsibility (CSR) (2017); establishment of the University of Gdańsk Committee for Social Responsibility (2019); adoption of the UG HR Development Policy (2021). The UG HR Development Policy regulates the issues of scientific career and promotion rules. It indicates three alternative academic career paths: research and teaching path, research path and teaching path. New rules for the periodic assessment of academic teachers were developed in 2021, taking into account the specificity of scientific disciplines – individual assessment criteria for each scientific discipline. Due to the great expectations of the academic community to regulate the issue of evaluation of scientific activities at the national level, considering the complexity of the assessment, reliability and transparency – in 2023 the University of Gdańsk joined the CoARA coalition, as the first classical university in Poland. Taking into account the importance of the next steps and the

significance of the reforms undertaken, a working group was established under the leadership of the Vice-Rector for Research, which developed the CoARA Action Plan.

ROAD MAP FOR THE REFORM OF ACADEMIC STAFF AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AT THE UNIVERSITY OF GDAŃSK IN THE YEARS 2024-28

❖ Action 1 – Reform of academic staff individual assessment

The goal is to develop a fair and balanced system of individual assessment of academic staff ensuring dynamic development of scientific disciplines while becoming independent from institutional evaluation.

Priorities:

- Identification of key challenges in changing the academic staff assessment system
- Changing existing internal regulations

Tasks:

conducting a survey on the strengths and weaknesses of the current academic staff assessment system among researchers representing all scientific disciplines at the University of Gdańsk	Q4 2024
developing objectives for the establishment of a new <i>Policy for the Development of Scientific Research</i> at the University of Gdańsk for 2025-2028	Q4 2024
preparation of survey results, additional focus groups, establishing the main axes of actions aimed at changing the assessment system	Q1 2025
development of a <i>Policy for the Development of Scientific Research</i> considering priorities resulting from the analysis of surveys regarding the assessment system, conclusions from focus groups and trends at leading universities in Europe	Q1 2025
conducting periodic assessment of all academic teachers in accordance with the principles currently in force	Q4 2025
summary of the periodic assessment conducted by the assessment committees in the context of planned changes	Q4 2025
development of new principles for the assessment of academic teachers for the years 2026-2030, taking into account all analyzed aspects and substantive and technical comments after the conducted assessment	Q4 2025

❖ Action 2 – Internal system for assessing the quality of scientific activities

The goal is to implement a system for assessing the quality of scientific activity at the faculties of the University of Gdańsk.

Priorities:

- Establishment of expert councils for scientific research at faculties
- Preparing councils for the first assessment of the quality of the faculties' scientific activities

Tasks:

introduction of regulations regarding the appointment of expert councils for scientific research into the Statute of the University of Gdańsk	Q2 2024
developing detailed rules for appointing and functioning of expert councils, including rules for assessment of the quality of the faculties' scientific activities	Q3 2024
appointment of expert council members	Q4 2024
training of expert councils' members, study visits at the University of Gdańsk	Q2-Q4 2025
first assessment of the quality of faculties' scientific activities; preparation of reports with recommendations by expert councils	Q4 2026
revision of the objectives for the functioning of expert councils	Q1 2027
second assessment of the quality of faculties' scientific activities; preparation of reports with recommendations by expert councils	Q4 2028

❖ **Action 3 – Actively shaping the national scientific research assessment system**

The goal is to participate in the discussion at the national and European levels regarding the development of the research assessment system.

Priorities:

- active participation in CoARA, including involvement in the work of the National Chapter
- participation in national consultations and discussions regarding the scientific research assessment system in Poland

The above-mentioned tasks will be conducted continuously in the years 2024-2028.

❖ **Supportive actions**

A. Introduction of training and support activities system (2024-2025)

- organization of monthly seminars "Fridays with science" – with the department of representatives of faculty authorities for research
- implementation of the electronic application for e-sabbatical leave
- seminars in the field of open science
- seminars in the field of social impact of research
- educational activities of the research ethics committee
- *Research Info Day* for newly hired employees
- exchange of experience in the field of good practices in the SEA-EU alliance
- expansion of the shared research infrastructure base

- adoption of the *Policy for Research Data Management* at the University of Gdańsk and a manual of good practices in this area
- B. Continuation of training, dissemination of knowledge on responsible assessment (2026-2028)
- seminars on the social impact of scientific research
 - work on the principles of using artificial intelligence in research – AI Policy
 - research using focus groups – identification of new challenges and benefits resulting from the implementation of the Action Plan
 - exchange of good practices within the National Chapter

EXISTING TOOLS AND PROCEDURES TO SUPPORT THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

- essential guide for a new UG employee
- platform – Knowledge Base – profiles of researchers and the ability to track scientific achievements
- bibliometric reports – Index Copernicus
- Code of Ethics of Academic Teachers of the University of Gdańsk
- HR Development Policy of the University of Gdańsk
- Policy for Research Development of the University of Gdańsk
- Policy on Counteracting the Conflict of Interest of the University of Gdańsk
- Policy of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Results

ENTITIES RESPONSIBLE FOR THE REALIZATION, COORDINATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ACTION PLAN

- Vice-Rector for Research
- CoARA Coordinator – Director of the Science Office
- Senate Committee for Science
- Section of Research Data Management and Open Science of the UG Library

